

Digitization of housing sector management

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Abstract: This article gives information about topical issues of the development of digital technologies in the field of real estate management in the different stages of the life cycle. The article investigates the possibilities of utilizing information modeling technology in the field of management of housing stock at the operational stage of its life cycle. This scientific research reveals the main advantages of using the information model of the object of real estate at the stage of operation, as well as recommendations on some issues related to the management of the housing stock of a large city. Based on the results of in-depth interviews, collection of expert assessments and field research of participants of the residential real estate market, we present conclusions on the degree of implementation of digital technologies in the field of housing construction and in the housing market. The overall result of the study is that almost all stages of the life cycle of a property are currently under information technologies and create a new ecosystem of the residential real estate market.

Keywords: housing stock, information modeling, digital technologies, housing and communal complex, real estate, investments, construction, control system, digitalization of real estate, information technology, blockchain, residential real estate market, housing construction.

I. Introduction

The creation of infrastructure elements of the "digital economy" is one of the main priorities of state policy. According to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, "Without the digital economy, there is no future for the economy countries". In order to accelerate the digitalization of the country, the head of state October 5, 2020 that approved the program "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" [1], also among the most important documents, we can also note the decree of the head of state of March 17, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of digital technologies in the city of Tashkent" [2]. The priority sectors for the implementation of the digital economy are construction, energy, agriculture and water management, transport, geology, cadastre, health care, education and archives.

The digitalization trend affects all sectors of the economy to varying degrees, and the sphere of housing and communal services, including the management of housing fund is no exception. It is widely known that information technology can improve the efficiency of the work of most city services and it reduces costs. In this connection, the modernization of housing stock management is decisive, that carried out by methodological and technological solutions, aimed at economic and information-analytical support management, including search, collection, processing, transformation, storage, distribution and use of data on each property. It is worth mentioning that

even in the context of a pandemic, the country carried out large-scale digital reforms and the importance of measures to wide introduction of digital technologies in various sectors of the economy.

II. Literature Review

According to the former Deputy Minister of Regional Development of the Russian Federation S.I. Kruglik "The housing sector is a multifaceted, complex system, the area of concentration not only of special economic, but also of special social interests, due to the primary importance of housing in people's lives" [3]. From proceeding we can conclude that the housing sector is the point where the interests of the population, business and government come into contact, which means different segments control theory.

According to the scientific works of Bardulin E.N., Stolbova O.G., Kartseva A.K., the management of the housing stock as "as a factor reflecting the degree and quality of social development of the country as a whole and an individual subject, which also are municipalities" [4]. However, management issues of the housing stock of a large city, remain still completely unresolved and this is due to the fact that the housing stock as an object of management is quite difficult.

Also, the issues of studying theoretical and scientific-methodological problems in the field of housing stock management is devoted to a number of scientific works of foreign scientists such as Raizberg B.A., Solow R.M., Twiss B., Friedman J., Asaul A.N., Baronin S.A., Vladimirova I.L., Gribovsky S.V., Zheleznyakov A.V. and many others [5]. Digital economy according to Professor B.N. Panshin "Economy, based on network services" [6]. In the scientific work of Professor E.A. Nesterenko and A.S. Gantry digital economy is understood as "a system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital information and communication technologies" [7]. Kosov and Yu.A. Kosova point out that the modern economy is of an open type and the importance of transparency of information is characteristic for many industries [8]. The role of digital technologies in economic activity and their application in the field of real estate management is devoted to the works of such scientists as Shine Pyter G., Schumpeter J., Azgaldov G.G., Baranova Yu., Kozlov I.M., Oganessian V.P., Sandram D., Safronov I.V. and many others [9].

Among the works of our scientists and economists, some aspects of the system management of housing stock and housing and communal services, of which noteworthy are the scientific works of such scientists as Nurimbetova R.I., Sultanova A.S., Matyakubova A.D., Tashmukhamedova K.S., Davletova I.Kh., Nabieva A.Kh., Tantybaeva K.A., Vishnevskaya N.M. and others [5,9]. Studing works of Uzbek, Russian and foreign researchers show what an important role in the formation of theoretical and practical aspects of housing stock management play information technology.

However, it should be noted that some methods have been introduced into management practice, housing stock in part and not fully studied. Thus, the relevance of the research topic is due to the need implementation of digital technologies for the formation of such a management system housing stock, which would ensure its effective functioning.

III. Research Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of scientific research was theoretical and methodological approaches to the definition of the concept of real estate, digital technologies for collecting and analyzing data on the housing stock, methodology management of the real estate market, substantiated in the scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists.

The study of applied aspects of housing stock management was carried out with using empirical and theoretical methods of knowledge such as observation, comparison, analysis, classification, analytical and statistical groupings. The information base of the scientific research was information about housing stock of the Republic of Uzbekistan and legal documents, including PP-5017 dated April 18, 2017 "On measures to further improve management of the system of housing and communal services" [10], PD-2922 dated 24 April 2017 "On measures to further improve the content system and operation of multi-apartment housing stock for the period 2017-

202" [11], PD-5152 dated June 19, 2021 "On further improvement of the system management of apartment buildings" [12].

IV. Analysis and results

The main emphasis in scientific research in the field of housing management fund in different countries of the world is done on the formation of the organizational foundations of management, determining the areas of activity of enterprises and types of services they provide in this area. In recent years, the focus has been on improving the quality and management efficiency of this activity, in particular, decentralization of housing stock management system and reduce state participation in management. Based on this, today it is of great importance to use modern methods in the management of the housing stock, the use of services of private sector enterprises in the implementation of management activities.

Despite the difficulties faced by every sector of the economy, the construction industry of Uzbekistan continues to develop dynamically, erected apartment buildings, a large-scale reconstruction of administrative buildings, international business centers are being built.

The program provides for three levels of development of the digital economy, which "in their close interaction affect the lives of citizens and society as a whole".

- markets and sectors of the economy;
- platforms and technologies where competencies are formed for the development of markets and sectors of the digital economy;
- an environment for the development of digital technology platforms and effective interaction between market entities.

Priority areas of state support are areas related to creating conditions for the development of the digital economy: legal regulation, personnel and education, support for specialized research and technological backlogs, as well as the development of basic infrastructure elements digital economy. The Program adopted 8 main digital technologies as the main ones:

- ✓ big data;
- ✓ neuro technologies and artificial intelligence;
- ✓ distributed ledger systems (block chain);
- ✓ quantum technologies;
- ✓ new production technologies;
- ✓ Internet;
- ✓ components of robotics and sensors;
- ✓ wireless communication technologies;
- ✓ virtual and augmented reality technologies.

Internet of Things and artificial intelligence - the foundation for a new generation of digital resources, robotics, drones and 3D printers are devices that contribute to the transfer of computer technology to the material world [13] (Piters, 2016). Augmented and virtual reality - technologies that combine the physical and digital worlds, block chain - a completely new approach to basic operations keeping records of commercial transactions [8] (Gareev, 2017).

Since the beginning of 2021, growth rates compared to the corresponding period of the previous year reached 100.8%. The industry is forecast to grow by several times, which will greatly increase flexibility and competitiveness. According to forecasts experts, the population of Uzbekistan may grow to 38 million people in the next five years. In this regard, the authorities are expanding the scale of housing construction. In 2021 year, within the framework of the mortgage program in the regions of Uzbekistan, 1,075 high-rise buildings (45.5 thousand apartments) in 207 blocks. When viewed in cross section statistics, which are shown in table 1, then for the last five years there was a significant increase in construction work in the Republic of Uzbekistan [13].

It should be noted that the housing stock is part of the construction industry, production as a system that includes both preparatory work in the construction period, as well as directly production processes at construction sites, as well as repair and construction works and reconstruction works in

building objects. Housing construction is a complex interrelated structure that includes a set of mechanisms for redistributing objects.

According to the Ministry of Housing and Communal Services as of 2021, there are 37,402 in the Republic of Uzbekistan apartment buildings, of which 68 percent are operated by partnerships, 24 percent by management companies, and 8 percent of houses do not have management. Moreover, there are 4,430 homeowners' associations, but statistics show that only 30 percent work satisfactorily [14]. Due to growth multi-apartment housing stock, as well as the physical deterioration of existing houses, homeowners, as well as management companies, have a number of problems related to maintenance, further use, repair and management. Therefore, to address these issues, it is considered necessary to create tool or system that would allow competently and effectively manage real estate, both privately and publicly owned.

In the digital economy, there is a digital transformation cities, which are defined under the term "smart city", they involve the use of digital technologies in city management, data innovations are primarily aimed at improving management efficiency, which in turn leads to an increase in resource savings and, as a result, improves the lives of citizens [15]. When it comes to digital technologies in the construction industry, the first we mean the trend of the present time - BIM technology (Building Information Modeling), which have already firmly entered life, since today it is impossible to imagine the implementation of any major project, where certain BIM solutions would not be involved. Worth for reference mention that Building Information Modeling (BIM) is a process based on the use of intelligent 3D models, with the help of using this technology, architecture and construction professionals can even more efficiently plan, design, build and operate buildings and facilities infrastructure [16].

Of course, large-scale work is underway in our country today to construction and commissioning of new buildings and structures, and these technologies open a lot of opportunities for a whole group of specialists from the architect ending with the manager of the projected building. But it is often believed that BIM technologies are needed only at the initial stages of the life of the projected buildings.

At present, the most developed world centers have already built, there are many that the first place there is not the erection and construction of new ones, but the maintenance of existing buildings and structures [17]. After all, the created Building Information Model has a much broader application. Including it is very useful for already existing objects, since it contains all necessary information. The life cycle of any construction object and associated with the information modeling process, there are two distinct large and very different stages in their essence - construction and operation, and each of them is controlled independently. In addition, at the same stage of operation is more complex and repeatedly involves steps to create (change) of an object. Information models depending on the stage of work with objects and tasks to be solved in world practice are usually divided into three types: design, construction and operational (Figure 1).

The operational information model of a building or structure allows solve problems such as ensuring the normal functioning of the building in accordance with its functional purpose, ensuring the planned operational characteristics of the object during the entire service life, ensuring established level of safety, ensuring trouble-free operation of engineering and technical systems of the building, maintaining the established internal climate (temperature and humidity conditions), as well as maintaining the normal sanitary and hygienic condition of the facility and the adjacent territory. Another obvious advantage of using this technology is the ability to simulate changes in the building structure, design re-equipment of the building with new engineering equipment, bringing it performance to the current level of requirements, track the current state of the building and timely take measures for major repairs or reconstruction, as well as competently operate existing facilities in housing stock. Thus, the use of digital technologies in particular information modeling at the stage of operation of a real estate object is a whole range of approaches to working with a structure, defined as solvable tasks and changing modeling technologies. Undoubtedly, the importance of information modeling technologies for areas of management of the housing stock and housing and communal services is an undeniable advantage today.

Firstly, BIM is very effective for the following building life cycles – its operation and service. Since repair and maintenance are permanent cost of the building that was put into operation. And having data from the information models, you can see the problems in a timely manner and rationally service.

Secondly, information modeling technology allows to calculate wear of materials, predict possible problems in operation even at the stage design model, take into account the difficulties with the service - make calculations for future stages. building life cycle. Laying down possible costs for case of repair or reconstruction of individual parts, as well as optimize energy-saving characteristics, based on the tasks of operation.

Thirdly, having a digital model, in other words, a "digital twin" building, its management and operation becomes more efficient and easier. Furthermore, the service life of systems or the entire building as a whole is increased, costs, and the overall quality of life of residents will improve. BIM in Building Operations has a specific practical value: thanks to a comprehensive system in virtual data from different specialists responsible for the project is selected, all elements of the future building are docked and coordinated.

V. Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the main part of the problems is related to lack of necessary and reliable information about real estate objects. Accordingly, the solution to these problems is seen in the creation of a unified information system on housing facilities, this platform and its implementation in the field of real estate management, will positively affect and will fundamentally change the collection, storage and use of information about objects real estate. To implement this idea, the author proposes the creation of electronic passports of real estate objects, which would also include digital models of buildings and structures and would be integrated with some kind of cartographic substrate for ease of use and orientation in space, such geographic information systems (hereinafter referred to as GIS) could serve as a platform, since a GIS works with all types of information that can be reflected on a map or diagram. This means that GIS is a technology by which combines traditional information management models with maps and databases data. The introduction of electronic passports would allow to combine existing documents certifying property rights, technical and cadastral passports into a completely new information management tool and would become main documents, the content of which will include the main technical, physical, economic characteristics of real estate objects, which required for monitoring and control.

Integration of a unified information system for managing the housing stock with cartographic services will allow solving such tasks as:

- inventory and accounting for all real estate objects located on the territory of the state;
- display of detailed attributive information on real estate objects;
- providing the necessary information for making management decisions, analysis of the situation on various topics based on available data;
- promotion effectiveness of interaction between public services and property owners, etc.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the digitalization of the sphere of housing management fund and housing sector. The first of all, improve the efficiency in management processes, which in turn would lead to a reduction in losses, a reduction indirect and overhead costs in tariffs, etc. Secondly, reducing the volume of receivables of the industry. Thirdly, ensuring transparency industry for public oversight and regulation; Fourthly, increasing the quality of housing and communal services provided by creating elements of market competition in the industry and, as a result, lower tariffs. In addition, it is an impetus to create conditions to attract private investment in the development of the industry and, finally, the formation of a database of complete, reliable and up-to-date real estate management data (on the state of the housing stock, the volume and quality of services provided and the consumption of energy resources, about consumers housing and communal services).

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